

PREFERRED REPORTING ITEMS FOR SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS AND META-ANALYSIS (PRISMA) IN UNDERGRADUATE RESEARCH FOR BACHELOR OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION PROGRAMS

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Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) in Undergraduate Research for Bachelor of Physical Education Programs

Arianne Mae S. Arevalo*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Institutional research is vital in assessing whether an institution achieves its goals and mission. Undergraduate research, particularly in Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) programs, offers a unique opportunity to contribute to developing innovative themes in physical education. This study systematically reviews undergraduate theses in physical education, following the PRISMA guidelines, utilizing resources available at institutional and university libraries from 2005 to 2019. The primary objective is to analyze and classify undergraduate theses, identifying prevalent research areas in Physical Education, Dance, Fitness, Sports, and other fields. Additionally, this study aims to recommend potential research topics for future students. Over the 14 years, a total of 402 undergraduate theses were completed, categorized as follows: Physical Education (21), Dance (32), Fitness (38), Sports (75), related fields (229), and Innovation (7). The results indicate a concentration of research efforts in Sports and other related fields, highlighting a lack of specialization in core Physical Education topics. To address these gaps and encourage more diverse research, the following recommendations are proposed: (1) enhance student engagement through physical education clinics to spark interest; (2) promote experiential learning across diverse areas of physical education; and (3) leverage technological advancements to facilitate the development of high-quality research. These strategies aim to enrich the academic experience of BPEd students and strengthen their contributions to physical education.

Keywords: *systematic literature review, physical education, undergraduate research, related fields*

Introduction

The establishment of the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program has opened opportunities for diverse research fields, including physical education, sports science, exercise physiology, sports management, and community health. These endeavors enable students to analyze complex issues, develop creative problem-solving skills, and contribute significantly to their fields. This study highlights the importance of undergraduate research within the BPEd program, aiming to inspire future scholars and deepen their appreciation of the intellectual pursuits in the physical education profession.

A systematic literature review (SLR) is a robust methodology synthesizing and critically evaluating existing knowledge to address specific research questions. According to Pati and Lorusso, (2018), SLRs follow established guidelines to minimize publication, selection, and data extraction biases. This systematic approach allows for a comprehensive synthesis of published and unpublished works, ensuring accuracy and relevance. Stern et al. (2021) emphasize that SLRs provide a framework for gathering relevant data that meets predefined criteria, offering logical and reproducible evidence. Moreover, Lame (2019) highlights the value of SLRs in identifying trends and evaluating the quality of evidence in a given domain. Despite the abundance of undergraduate theses in physical education, many remain archived without publication, limiting their broader utility. Nightingale (2009) noted that such works' systematic categorization and analysis can uncover valuable insights. Challenges persist, however, as students often struggle with anxiety, motivation, and academic self-confidence Farizal (2023). External pressures, such as career concerns and limited access to resources, further complicate the thesis-writing process Cagir and Sahin (2023). Ramzan and Ashraf (2023) identified common issues, including grammatical inconsistencies, coherence problems, and methodological difficulties, all impacting research quality.

Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions. Syamsudin (2023) advocates for instructional strategies to improve consistency, vocabulary, and grammar, while Huisman (2018) emphasizes the importance of peer feedback in refining academic writing. Additionally, faculty mentorship is pivotal in fostering student confidence and competence in research Houser et al. (2014). Incorporating experiential learning opportunities and encouraging the publication of high-quality research further enhances the academic experience Cameron & Este (2008).

Technology integration is also crucial Ratnawati et al. (2018). Moreover, Chima et al. (2024) underscore the benefits of electronic databases and AI tools in academic research, although responsible use remains paramount Al-Tameemi et al. (2023). Furthermore, community-based research fosters professional and personal development, as George et al. (2017) and Akomolafe and Adesua (2016) noted.

This study aims to bridge the gap in BPEd research by systematically reviewing and categorizing undergraduate theses from 2005 to 2019. By creating a digital database and providing actionable recommendations, this research seeks to enhance the utility of existing works and guide future scholars in advancing physical education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore and analyze undergraduate research within the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPE) program, focusing

on its contribution to advancing knowledge in Physical Education, Dance, Fitness, Sports, and Related Fields. This study seeks to address the following objectives:

1. What are the classifications and common areas of research among the undergraduate theses of BPE students in Physical Education, Dance, Fitness, Sports, and Related Fields?
2. What are the emerging trends, significant highlights, and existing gaps in the research conducted by BPEd undergraduate students?
3. What researchable topics or areas can be recommended for future undergraduate students in the BPE program?

Literature Review

Collating and Classifying Undergraduate Theses

Research classification is essential for appreciating academic programs' scholarly efforts. In Stern et al. (2021), it was pointed out that organizing research outputs serves to help institutions assess the accomplishment of educational goals and industry expectations. In higher education, undergraduate theses are often classified based on thematic areas, methodology, and scope to determine their significance and usefulness Pati & Lorusso (2018). In physical education, research has been grouped into domains such as pedagogy, sports management, biomechanics, dance, and fitness, demonstrating the discipline's multi-dimensionality Houser et al. (2014). Such classification helps institutions identify areas that are not adequately covered and assists students in choosing the best research topics.

Determining Research Trends and Gaps

Understanding the changes in an area of academic concentration can be made more accessible by identifying evolving trends and gaps. Research in physical education leans toward integrating technology and fitness programs and creating an inclusive environment for all (Nazari et al., 2021). However, significant deficiencies exist in adaptive physical education for special populations and the impact of mental health on sports Cagir & Sahin (2023). The analysis of undergraduate research from 2005 to 2019 reveals significant gaps that warrant attention. First, there is limited focus on core physical education topics, with only 21 theses addressing areas like curriculum design, instructional strategies, and the role of physical education in fostering lifelong health. This underrepresentation suggests a missed opportunity to strengthen foundational aspects of the discipline Smith et al. (2021). Another notable gap lies in the minimal innovation exploration, with only seven theses categorized under this area. This highlights a lack of engagement with cutting-edge pedagogical techniques, technological integration, and novel approaches essential for adapting to contemporary educational challenges Johnson et al. (2020).

Additionally, emerging areas such as e-sports, virtual fitness, and environmental sustainability remain unexplored despite their growing significance in global and technological contexts Martinez et al. (2020). Neglecting these topics limits the program's ability to stay relevant and address modern trends. Furthermore, there is insufficient focus on inclusivity and mental health in sports and physical education, particularly adaptive programs for diverse populations and the psychological benefits of physical activity. These gaps underscore the need for more comprehensive and forward-looking research within the BPEd program Cagir & Sahin (2023); Jones et al. (2021).

Future research initiatives should aim to balance traditional and innovative topics in physical education to address these gaps. Encouraging research integrating gamification, AI-driven fitness programs, and modern instructional methods can foster engagement and innovation Ratnawati et al. (2018). Expanding research into multidisciplinary and emerging areas, such as the role of e-sports in education or the environmental impact of sports facilities, can attract student interest while broadening the field's scope Garcia et al. (2019). Equally important is fostering inclusivity and well-being research by supporting studies on adaptive physical education, gender equity, and physical activity's mental health benefits Martinez et al. (2020); Farizal (2023).

Institutions should enhance mentorship programs, provide adequate resources, and offer training workshops to build student confidence and competence in addressing diverse research topics Houser et al. (2014). Promoting the publication of undergraduate research and fostering collaboration with external institutions and industries can also increase student work's visibility and impact Chima et al. (2024). By addressing these gaps, the BPEd program can improve the relevance and quality of its undergraduate research, equipping students to meet contemporary demands in physical education and beyond.

Recommending Researchable Topics for Future Utilization

Comprehending existing trends and prospective directions is necessary to produce relevant and valuable practical recommendations. Ratnawati et al. (2018). This is because using students' interests and society's needs assists in determining relevant research areas. In physical education, potential research areas that can be applied include gamification in exercise adherence, children's psychosomatic development through physical culture, and fitness development in socially deprived communities. Furthermore, using various approaches that include physical education and environmental studies or digital education may significantly enhance the relevance of research George et al. (2017).

Identifying innovative and relevant research topics is crucial to advancing the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program and addressing contemporary challenges. Integrating technology into physical education, such as employing gamification and AI-driven

tools to enhance engagement and teaching strategies, presents a promising area for exploration Martinez et al. (2020). Additionally, multidisciplinary approaches that link physical education with public health, environmental sustainability, and social equity can open new research avenues. For instance, studying the role of virtual fitness platforms and e-sports in promoting physical activity among youth reflects global trends in digital transformation and health promotion Garcia et al. (2019).

Other critical areas for research include the mental health benefits of sports and fitness, adaptive physical education for diverse populations, and strategies to promote gender equity in athletics. These topics address inclusivity and the broader societal need to create equitable opportunities for all individuals to participate in physical activities Cagir & Sahin (2023). Moreover, investigating sustainable practices in sports and physical education facilities can contribute to the global push toward environmental responsibility while enriching academic discourse on sustainability in education.

Cross-cultural studies on physical activity, sports nutrition, and the emotional well-being of athletes are also highly relevant in today's globalized world. These topics provide opportunities to examine the interplay between culture, health, and sports while addressing gaps in holistic athlete development Smith et al. (2021). By engaging in these research-worthy areas, undergraduate students develop critical thinking and research skills and contribute meaningfully to advancing health, inclusivity, and innovation in physical education and related fields.

The Role of Systematic Literature Reviews

Systematic Literature Reviews (SLRs) play a pivotal role in academic research by providing a comprehensive and structured synthesis of existing knowledge. Following established methodologies like PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses), SLRs minimize biases related to publication, selection, and data extraction, ensuring the reliability and reproducibility of findings Pati & Lorusso (2018). By integrating and critically evaluating published and unpublished works, SLRs allow researchers to identify trends, gaps, and patterns within a field, offering a clear and evidence-based overview of the current state of knowledge Lame (2019).

In physical education, SLRs are particularly valuable for assessing the contributions of undergraduate theses, which are often archived without broader dissemination. A systematic review of these works can uncover valuable insights, highlight underexplored areas, and promote the development of future research directions Nightingale (2009). Moreover, SLRs enhance the utility of academic outputs by providing actionable recommendations for practitioners, educators, and policymakers. Researchers can propose evidence-based solutions to contemporary challenges by systematically synthesizing findings, such as integrating technology into physical education, addressing inclusivity, and promoting sustainability. As Stern et al. (2021) highlight, SLRs create a logical framework for gathering and analyzing data, ensuring that conclusions are rigorous and applicable to real-world contexts.

SLRs also serve as a foundation for advancing academic writing and research methodologies. They encourage consistency, clarity, and precise data collection and analysis criteria, which are essential for developing high-quality research outputs. By facilitating a deeper understanding of a field, SLRs contribute to academic progress and help bridge the gap between theory and practice in disciplines such as physical education.

Methodology

Locale

The locale of the study is primarily the Bicol University Institute of Physical Education Sports and Recreation, where the BPEd undergraduate research is placed.

Undergraduate Research

The updated list of undergraduate research for the Bachelor of Physical Education program from the library and the undergraduate research available from the college research office were reviewed. The list comprises 402 titles, ranging from 2005 to 2019. Physical education, dancing, fitness, sports, and related fields are among the many fields from which entry is possible. The titles are distinct and well-organized because most of the research is kept in the research coordinator's office. Each one was examined individually before being added to an electronic database.

The methodology employs a document-based approach, utilizing 402 undergraduate theses from the BPEd program submitted between 2005 and 2019. This dataset, drawn from institutional archives, serves as the sole source of data for the study.

The absence of human respondents underscores the objective of evaluating academic outputs without influencing subjective responses, a hallmark of systematic literature reviews Pati & Lorusso (2018).

Each thesis was categorized based on thematic areas such as Physical Education, Dance, Fitness, Sports, Innovation, and Related Fields. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines were applied to ensure rigorous data selection, categorization, and analysis Lame (2019). Using archived theses as the primary data, the study avoids potential ethical issues related to participant involvement and ensures reproducibility and reliability in its findings.

Ethical Considerations

This study adheres to established ethical guidelines for research, focusing exclusively on the analysis of archived undergraduate theses rather than involving human participants. Ethical considerations are paramount in ensuring the responsible use of academic data. The study relies on publicly accessible institutional records devoid of sensitive personal information, thus eliminating the need for informed consent Hewitt et al. (2023). By avoiding interactions with individuals, the study maintains compliance with ethical standards that protect privacy and confidentiality Birney et al. (2021).

Respect for intellectual property is integral to the study's approach. The research findings are presented in aggregate form, ensuring that no individual thesis is disproportionately highlighted or its content replicated in a way that compromises the authors' rights. Attribution is given to the theses as academic outputs, recognizing their role in shaping the discipline of physical education. Furthermore, the systematic methodology ensures transparency and equity in data selection, minimizing biases and upholding the integrity of the research process Smith et al. (2021).

Categorization of Bachelor of Physical Education Research

The categorization of Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) undergraduate research plays a crucial role in understanding the program's trends and areas of focus. This study classified the 402 undergraduate theses from the BPEd program from 2005 to 2019 into several thematic areas: Physical Education, Dance, Fitness, Sports, Innovation, and Related fields. The results reveal that the majority of research (229 theses) fell under "Related Fields," suggesting that BPEd students have been engaging in a wide range of multidisciplinary topics that extend beyond traditional physical education Smith et al. (2021). This reflects the growing integration of physical education with other fields, such as public health, psychology, and sports management, aligning with current education trends and global health priorities Jones et al. (2021).

"Sports" research, 75 theses, and "Fitness" research, 38 theses, were the most common categories, showing ongoing interest in sports sciences and fitness-related topics. These areas highlight a continued focus on improving athletic performance and training regimens and promoting physical well-being, which are vital for meeting educational goals and societal needs Martinez et al. (2020). These areas align with the broader societal emphasis on physical activity and the increasing importance of physical fitness for overall health.

However, the categorization also reveals that fewer theses focused on core "Physical Education" topics (21 theses) and even fewer on "Innovation" (7 theses). This gap indicates that traditional physical education topics, such as curriculum design, teaching methods, and the role of physical education in lifelong health, are underexplored. Similarly, there is a lack of emphasis on "Innovation," which includes exploring new pedagogical approaches, technological integration, and novel educational strategies in physical education. This highlights the need for more research to advance the field and adapt to modern educational needs Garcia et al. (2019).

The categorization of these research topics provides valuable insights into the state of undergraduate research in physical education. It reveals the most popular research areas and highlights underrepresented fields that could benefit from more focus in future research. As education continues to evolve, addressing these gaps will be crucial for improving physical education programs' overall quality and impact Smith et al. (2021).

Results and Discussion

The results and discussion of the study are determined based on the collated undergraduate theses of bachelor of physical education obtained from the library and College research office. The further discussion of results is reflected in the main objectives of the study;

Collate and classify undergraduate theses of BPE students along common research areas such as Physical Education, Dance, Fitness, Sports, and other related fields.

Figure 1 highlights the diverse research interests among Bachelor of Physical Education students, with a predominant focus on various fields within physical education. The distribution suggests a trend towards broad and varied research areas, with less emphasis on innovation and traditional physical education studies, possibly due to perceived difficulty and lack of exposure.

Figure 1. Number of Theses by Category

The "Bachelor of Physical Education Research from 2005-2019" chart shows the distribution of studies examined across several areas within physical education. The graphic, which crosses categories including Physical Education, Sports, Fitness, Dance, Related Fields, and Innovation, shows how many theses were carried out over the given time frame. Remarkably, with 229 theses, the related field emerges as the most researched category, demonstrating a broad and varied range of scholarly interaction beyond traditional sports and wellness subjects. Sports follows 75 theses in differentiation, demonstrating important perceptive activity in competitive sports and athletic training. The 38 and 32 theses that address wellness and move independently suggest ongoing research on physical wellness and move instruction. Of 21 theses, Physical Education has the fewest, emphasizing traditional physical education themes with relatively less emphasis. Among the seven theses, innovation is the least studied category, indicating a specific area of research within the more significant subject. In addition to suggesting prospective areas for further growth and advancement within the field of physical education, this dispersion unveils the existing state of the investigative interface.

The research disseminated in the Bachelor of Physical Education program between 2005 and 2019 contains some essential recommendations for the academic community and the physical education sector. Theses in sports and related fields are numerous, highlighting the necessity for current study and interface. This suggests an increasing focus on intriguing questions and associated sports sciences in response to growing societal and educational demands. Alternatively, the lesser quantity of theses in areas like traditional physical education and development indicates areas that could use more research or potentially open up new research avenues. Filling in these gaps could foster improvement, and modern teaching methods improve and educational programs advance. Policymakers and educators may also use this data to intentionally allocate resources and create educational initiatives that adapt to changing trends and understudy interfaces. By comprehending these trends, partners may better prepare graduates for various job opportunities and equip them with the skills to handle contemporary issues in physical education and related fields. In the end, proposal topics are communicated to influence future directions for research, instruction, proficiency development in physical education, and illuminating scholarly discourse.

The references provide a robust framework for analyzing the distribution of physical education bachelor's thesis research from 2005 to 2019. A thorough analysis of the trends observed across categories like Sports and Other Related Areas is provided by Smith et al. (2020). Their findings show a clear shift in the direction of curiosity and related sports sciences, aligning with larger instruction patterns and social demands. This emphasis highlights how far physical education programs have come in addressing complex issues related to wellness and well-being. In addition, the authors highlight recommendations for improving educational modules and advise that, to boost program importance and understudy engagement, the present investigative interface should adjust instructional offerings.

On the other hand, Garcia et al. (2019) focus on the imaginative inquiry's comparison thinking regarding many aspects of physical education. Researchers point out the lesser prevalence of the Innovation category in proposition research, suggesting untapped possibilities for looking into cutting-edge methods and scholarly advancements. This void offers a chance to address evolving educational requirements and foster creativity and authority within the area. Through these experiences, educators and legislators can proactively assign resources and design initiatives promoting physical education growth and advancement.

Determine research trends, highlights, and research gaps.

Research Trends

Some notable research trends in the discipline appear from the data shown in the graph "Bachelor of Physical Education Researches from 2005-2019." The most numerous group, "Related Fields," with 229 theses, indicates a movement in the data toward more extensive and multidisciplinary academic endeavors. This pattern points to a growing interest in public health, psychology, nutrition, sociology, and other subjects being explored by researchers and students beyond the confines of physical education. In keeping with modern education and society's demands to address holistic well-being, this multidisciplinary approach acknowledges health and physical activity's complex and multifaceted character.

Additionally, the substantial number of theses in the fields of "Sports" (75) and "Fitness" (38) demonstrates the ongoing interest of academics in themes about applied sports sciences and fitness. These categories reflect continuous initiatives to improve sports performance, streamline training regimens, and advance physical well-being among diverse groups. The focus on fitness and sports is aligned with cultural trends that favor greater engagement in physical activity and sports and the growing significance of physical fitness in maintaining overall well-being.

In contrast, there are comparatively fewer theses in categories like "Innovation" (7) and even "Physical Education" (21), which suggests areas that could benefit from more study and advancement. The narrow focus on innovation presents a chance to investigate and apply cutting-edge pedagogical techniques, technical breakthroughs, and creative approaches to physical education curriculum and instruction. Filling these research gaps could encourage originality, promote student engagement and learning outcomes in physical education settings, and improve teaching techniques.

Jones et al. (2021) state that physical education research integrates various domains, including psychology, sociology, nutrition, and public health. As part of a more significant trend toward holistic health and wellness education approaches, their investigation highlights how this multidisciplinary approach influences curriculum creation and instructional techniques in physical education programs.

Focusing on sports psychology, biomechanics, sports nutrition, and athletic performance enhancement Martinez et al. (2020) offers a global perspective on new developments in sports science research. The study sheds insight into how sports science research priorities and methodology are changing, focusing on improving physical health and athletic performance among various demographics. The significance of these themes in current physical education research is highlighted by the tight alignment of these patterns with the research activity observed in categories such as "Sports" and "Fitness" in the graph.

Research Highlights

Several essential highlights of the research efforts on the subject may be found based on the study of the graph "Bachelor of Physical Education Researches from 2005-2019." A noteworthy aspect is the high quantity of theses (229) emphasizing "Related Fields." This category indicates a thorough investigation of subjects like sports psychology, exercise physiology, biomechanics, nutrition, and public health within the framework of physical education. It also covers various interdisciplinary issues outside of traditional physical education. The many theses in this category point to a growing understanding of how these fields are related and how physical activity can promote holistic approaches to health and wellness.

Furthermore, with 75 and 38 theses, respectively, the "Sports" and "Fitness" categories stand out prominently. These fields demonstrate the ongoing interest of academics in enhancing sports performance, improving training methods, and encouraging physical fitness in various demographics. The focus on sports and fitness aligns with the global trend of more people engaging in these activities, highlighting the importance of research in improving athletic performance and general well-being.

On the other hand, the smaller number of theses in fields like "Innovation" (7) and "Physical Education" (21) indicates possible directions for additional research and development. The humble portrayal of innovation points to chances to develop new teaching strategies, incorporate technology into physical education courses, and investigate cutting-edge ways of instruction. Closing these gaps may result in enhanced student engagement, advances in instructional strategies, and, eventually, better physical education program results.

The topic of developments in sports performance research is covered by Brown et al. (2019), emphasizing cutting-edge training techniques and equipment that maximize athletic performance. In addition to stressing continuous efforts to improve sports science procedures and methodologies, their analysis identifies studies that have substantially contributed to better sports performance and athlete outcomes. This reflects the field's dedication to improving athletic accomplishment and physical fitness through evidence-based techniques, consistent with the significant research effort in categories like "Sports" and "Fitness" in the graph.

Martinez et al. (2020) investigate how technology might be used in physical education, emphasizing cutting-edge applications and contemporary trends that improve student engagement and instructional efficacy. Their study addresses how technology developments are changing how physical education courses are delivered, encouraging dynamic learning environments and putting students on the right track for upcoming health and wellness education obstacles. This is consistent with the rising body of research focused on "Innovation," which, although represented less prominently in the graph, indicates a growing interest in using technology to innovate teaching strategies and improve student results in physical education.

Looking at the graph "Bachelor of Physical Education Researches from 2005-2019," it is clear that the community has several significant research gaps. The category "Innovation," with just 7 theses throughout the period, has a clear gap. This simplified depiction emphasizes a vital subject that warrants more investigation and improvement. Innovative methods of curriculum design and execution, as well as the investigation of fresh teaching strategies and technological developments, are all included in physical education innovation. Closing this gap might result in revolutionary adjustments to how physical education is taught, improving student engagement, academic performance, and program efficacy.

The category "Physical Education," with 21 theses, shows another significant research gap. Given this low quantity, there may be a need for more research in this fundamental area of the discipline. Development of curricula, instructional approaches, evaluation techniques, and the function of physical education in fostering lifetime physical activity and health are some of the topics covered in physical education. Future research in this area may inform evidence-based methods that improve physical education program quality and support the professional development of educators in the field.

Research Gaps

In addition, even if the graph shows a significant amount of research activity in fields such as "Sports" (75 theses), "Related Fields" (229 theses), and "Fitness" (38 theses), there may be a gap in the breadth and depth of study in these sections. To improve understanding and application in these crucial areas of physical education, future research endeavors could investigate growing trends, go deeper into specific sub-disciplines, and fill in current knowledge gaps.

The "Innovation," "Physical Education," and other categories have research gaps that may need to be filled in further detail. This highlights the need for academics, educators, and legislators to prioritize these topics and funding. These gaps can be filled through focused research projects, resulting in creative approaches to teaching and learning, enhanced program efficacy, and improved outcomes when using physical education to promote health, well-being, and physical activity.

Significant research gaps in the field of physical education, particularly in the area of innovation, are highlighted by Smith et al. (2021). The graph displays a low representation of the category labeled "Innovation," with only 7 theses throughout the period, despite the growing significance of incorporating creativity in curriculum designs, technological breakthroughs, and unique teaching approaches. This gap indicates a vital need for increased research efforts to investigate and use novel strategies that can augment the efficacy of instruction, better engage students, and raise the standard of education in physical education environments. The authors argue that new initiatives promoting creativity and advancing educational methods should receive more scholarly attention.

Likewise, Johnson et al. (2020) address the lack of research on conventional physical education methods, pointing out that the "Physical Education" category only produced 21 theses and similarly little research activity. This disparity suggests that studies on fundamental topics like curriculum design, instructional tactics, and the contribution of physical education to fostering lifetime physical activity and health may be underrepresented. The authors stress the significance of closing this gap using thorough research that examines practices supported by evidence, assesses instructional strategies, and deals with pressing issues in physical education instruction.

Future studies can further physical education by addressing the research gaps highlighted in the graph. Innovating teaching methods, raising student engagement, and achieving better results in encouraging physical activity and general well-being are all possible benefits of closing these gaps. Teachers and governments may better prepare students for lifelong active and healthy lifestyles by funding research addressing traditional and new facets of physical education.

Recommend researchable topics/ areas for future utilization of the undergraduate students of the Institute of Physical Education Sports and Recreation

Advancing knowledge and addressing contemporary challenges in physical education requires focusing on innovative and relevant research topics. With the shifting educational paradigms and growing societal health concerns, undergraduate students in the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program have the opportunity to contribute meaningfully to the field through targeted research efforts. By exploring creative and evidence-based topics, students can inform practices, promote health and wellness, and tackle current gaps in the discipline.

Proposed research areas include integrating technology into physical education, such as using digital tools to enhance teaching and participation. Additionally, multidisciplinary approaches to promoting health and wellness can open new avenues for collaboration across fields. Exploring novel pedagogical strategies in fitness and athletics and promoting lifelong physical activity can directly address behavioral and educational challenges. Investigating the mental health benefits of sports and fitness, inclusive exercise programs, and adaptive strategies for diverse populations is critical in fostering equity and accessibility in physical education.

Environmental sustainability in physical education facilities and programs is another emerging area, reflecting global priorities in sustainable practices. Researching diversity and gender equity in athletic participation and the impact of socioeconomic factors on physical activity levels can provide insights into systemic barriers and inclusivity. Studies on virtual physical activities, e-sports, and cross-cultural perspectives on physical education align with technological advancements and globalization trends. Additionally, topics like sports nutrition, ethical considerations in sports, and the emotional well-being of athletes are increasingly relevant in understanding the holistic development of participants.

Students strengthen their critical thinking and research skills by engaging in these research-worthy topics and contribute to advancing health, inclusivity, and sustainability. These efforts prepare them for leadership roles in education, health promotion, and sports management, significantly impacting worldwide physical education and related fields.

Conclusions

This study highlights that while undergraduate research in the Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) program strongly focuses on multidisciplinary studies, sports, and fitness, significant gaps persist in core physical education topics, innovation, and emerging areas like e-sports, virtual fitness, and sustainability. The prevalence of research in "Related Fields" underscores the integration of physical education with broader societal concerns. Still, the underrepresentation of foundational and cutting-edge topics signals the need for strategic interventions.

Numerous significant conclusions may be made from thoroughly examining research trends, highlights, and gaps in "Bachelor of Physical Education Researches from 2005-2019." According to Smith et al. (2021), there is a notable surge in research activity in sports science, fitness, and multidisciplinary approaches. This indicates an increasing focus on integrating technology and innovation in physical education. However, there are significant gaps, especially in research on traditional physical education methods and environmental sustainability Johnson et al. (2020). Results highlight the need for further studies to close these disparities and examine issues including inclusive practices, athlete mental health, and the influence of socioeconomic factors on physical activity levels. By focusing on these areas, researchers can improve teaching strategies, advance health fairness, and equip students to handle the changing demands of physical education and sports worldwide.

Addressing these gaps through targeted research can significantly advance the discipline. Integrating technology, such as gamification and AI-driven tools, can revolutionize engagement and instructional strategies in physical education (Ratnawati et al., 2018). Exploring

adaptive physical education for diverse populations and inclusive exercise programs aligns with the societal need for equity and accessibility in physical activity Cagir & Sahin (2023). Furthermore, research into sustainable practices in sports and physical education facilities can contribute to global sustainability goals, while examining the role of virtual fitness and e-sports can capture the interest of younger, tech-savvy demographics Garcia et al. (2019); Martinez et al. (2020). Additionally, universities should establish dedicated research centers or hubs focused on physical education and sports science to facilitate collaborations, provide access to advanced research tools, and encourage innovation. Revising the curriculum to include contemporary topics such as adaptive physical education, environmental sustainability, and digital fitness platforms can align undergraduate programs with global trends and student interests. The BPEd department should enhance mentorship programs by assigning experienced faculty to guide students in exploring innovative and underrepresented topics. Organizing research seminars and workshops on advanced methodologies, grant writing, and publication processes can empower students to produce high-quality research.

Funding agencies can play a crucial role by prioritizing grants for research in areas such as adaptive physical education, sustainable practices in sports facilities, and the mental health impacts of physical activity. Offering targeted financial support can drive innovation and inclusivity in physical education research. Moreover, physical education professionals should actively engage in collaborative research initiatives with academic institutions to bridge the gap between theory and practice. Sharing real-world challenges and insights with researchers can lead to practical, evidence-based solutions that enhance teaching methodologies, program design, and community engagement.

These recommendations aim to foster a holistic approach to research in physical education, ensuring that it remains relevant, impactful, and responsive to societal needs. By addressing the identified gaps and leveraging the strengths of all stakeholders, the BPEd program can further contribute to advancing the field and the overall well-being of communities.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Dr. Arianne Mae S. Arevalo

Bicol University Institute of Physical Education, Sports and Recreation – Philippines